

**PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT AND PERFORMANCE INDICATORS AMONG THE
PUBLIC ELEMENTARY AND SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN SARIAYA EAST
DISTRICT, DIVISION OF QUEZON: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED
INTERVENTION PROGRAM**

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ABSTRACT

This quantitative research investigates the relationship between parental engagement and school performance in public elementary and secondary schools within Sariaya East District, Division of Quezon. Utilizing a stratified sampling technique, the study selected parents from fourteen public elementary schools and four public secondary schools as respondents. The research instrument consisted of a self-made questionnaire with two parts: one assessing parental engagement across various domains and another determining performance indicators of the schools. Data gathering involved proposal defense, correspondence with district supervisors and school principals, administering questionnaires, and obtaining performance data from schools. Statistical analysis was conducted using Microsoft Excel, employing descriptive statistics and non-parametric tests including the Kruskal-Wallis H-test and Spearman rank-order correlation. The findings reveal varying degrees of parental engagement across different schools and significant differences in responses. Spearman rank-order correlation analysis indicates a significant relationship between parental engagement and school performance. The study contributes to understanding the dynamics between parental engagement and school performance, offering insights for educational stakeholders to enhance collaboration between schools and parents. Limitations include the reliance on self-reported data and the generalizability of findings beyond the study locale. Future research could explore additional factors influencing parental engagement and its impact on educational outcomes.

Keywords: *School Performance, Parental Engagement, Home Engagement, School Engagement, and Child Invitation*

INTRODUCTION

School performance is a crucial measure of educational effectiveness, encompassing various indicators such as academic achievement, graduation rates, and attendance records. In countries like Cambodia and the Philippines, challenges persist in ensuring quality education and improving learning outcomes despite significant efforts to enhance access to primary education. In 2020, the Philippines made significant progress in providing access to primary education. However, challenges persist in early childhood care and development, internal efficiency, and learning outcomes, as noted in the NCEFA 2019 report. Through the government's efforts to achieve the MDG targets, recent studies such as the Philippines Midterm Progress Report on the MDGs assess that the probability of achieving universal primary education in the country is low (based on net enrollment rate, cohort survival rate, and completion rate). The EFA Global Monitoring Report (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2017) highlighted that from 1999 to 2016, the Philippines experienced a decline in its net enrollment rate, placing it among the countries with the highest number of out-of-school children, exceeding 500,000. Parental engagement emerges as a critical factor influencing students' academic success, as observed through social learning theories emphasizing parents' role as primary role models. Active parental involvement in children's education positively correlates with academic performance and fosters a supportive learning environment (Garcia, L. M., & Santos, A. C., 2020).

Legislative efforts like the No Child Left Behind Act (Peterson, 2003) underscore the importance of parental engagement in shaping the quality of school teaching and learning processes. However, disparities in parental engagement exist across different types of schools, highlighting the need for comprehensive research to understand its impact on school performance. Existing literature often overlooks detailed comparisons of parental engagement between elementary and secondary schools, as well as factors influencing these differences. Such understanding is essential for principals and educators to tailor communication strategies, provide transition support, and enhance parent satisfaction and retention rates. This study aims to fill these gaps by investigating the relationship between parental engagement and school performance in public elementary and secondary schools within the Sariaya East District. The findings will inform the development of a Parental Engagement Program, contributing to improved educational outcomes and stronger partnerships between schools and parents.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the relationship between Parental Engagement and School Performance among the Public Elementary and Secondary Schools in Sariaya East District, Division of Quezon.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of Parental Engagement in the following level of schools in Sariaya East District, Division of Quezon:
 - 1.1 Elementary
 - 1.1.1 Home Engagement
 - 1.1.2 School Engagement
 - 1.1.3 Response to Child's Invitation
 - 1.1.4 Response to Teacher's Invitation
 - 1.1.5 Response to General School Invitation
 - 1.2 Secondary
 - 1.2.1 Home Engagement
 - 1.2.2 School Engagement
 - 1.2.3 Response to Child's Invitation
 - 1.2.4 Response to Teacher's Invitation
 - 1.2.5 Response to General School Invitation
2. What are the Performance Indicators of the following level of schools in Sariaya East District in terms of:
 - 2.1 Elementary
 - 2.1.1 Enrolment Rate
 - 2.1.2 Promotion Rate
 - 2.1.3 Retention Rate
 - 2.1.4 Dropout Rate
 - 2.1.5 Graduation Rate
 - 2.2 Secondary
 - 2.2.1 Enrolment Rate
 - 2.2.2 Promotion Rate
 - 2.2.3 Retention Rate
 - 2.2.4 Dropout Rate
 - 2.2.5 Graduation Rate
3. Is there a significant relationship between parental engagement and performance indicators in public elementary and secondary schools in the Sariaya East District?
4. Is there a significant difference between parental engagement in elementary and secondary schools in Sariaya East District?
 - 4.1 Elementary
 - 4.1.1 Home Engagement
 - 4.1.2 School Engagement
 - 4.1.3 Response to Child's Invitation
 - 4.1.4 Response to Teacher's Invitation
 - 4.1.5 Response to General School Invitation
 - 4.2 Secondary
 - 4.2.1 Home Engagement
 - 4.2.2 School Engagement
 - 4.2.3 Response to Child's Invitation
 - 4.2.4 Response to Teacher's Invitation
 - 4.2.5 Response to General School Invitation
5. Is there a significant difference in the Performance Indicators between the Public Elementary and Secondary Schools in Sariaya East District?

- 5.1 Enrolment Rate
- 5.2 Promotion Rate
- 5.3 Retention Rate
- 5.4 Dropout Rate
- 5.5 Graduation Rate

6. What intervention program could be devised based on the study's findings?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research study is quantitative. According to Kothari (2023), it is a research design used to obtain evidence of cause and effect relationship between two or more variables, where one/some variable/s would be the dependent and another/rest of the variable would be the independent ones. Meanwhile, since this research aims to know the relationship between parental engagement and internal efficiency among the public elementary and secondary schools in Sariaya East District, the abovementioned design is deemed the most appropriate research design.

Research Locale

The research was carried out in fourteen (14) public elementary schools in Sariaya East, namely: Antipolo Elementary School, Balubal- Gibanga Elementary School, Bucal Elementary School, Canda Elementary School, Castanas, Elementary School, Jose Rizal Elementary School, Manuel L. Quezon Elementary School, Morong Elementary School, Pantoc Elementary School, Pili Elementary School, Sariaya East Central Elementary School, Talaan Elementary School, Tumbaga 1 Elementary School and Tumbaga 2 Elementary School and four (4) Public Secondary Schools in Sariaya East District namely: Canda National High School, Sariaya National High School, Pili National High School, and Castanas National High School. The said schools are located in Sariaya East District and are considered well-established public elementary and secondary schools in the Division of Quezon. The researcher opted to conduct the study in the following public elementary and secondary schools to know the relationship between parental engagement and school performance in their respective institutions.

Population and Sampling

A stratified sampling technique was used to get the respondents from the fourteen (14) main public elementary and four (4) public secondary schools in Sariaya East District. The researcher got the total population of the participating institutions and utilized Slovin's formula with a 5% margin of error and stratified sample formula to obtain the desired sample size that served as the respondents of the study. Slovin's formula is a formula if a sample is taken from the population and when considering the confidence level and margin of error.

The respondents of the study were selected parents from eighteen (18) public elementary schools and four (4) Public Secondary Schools in Sariaya East District, Division of Quezon.

School Level	Name of School	Number of Enrolees	Number of Respondents
Elementary	Antipolo Elementary School	261	22
	Balubal- Gibanga Elementary School	499	15
	Bucal Elementary School	505	22
	Canda Elementary School	920	22
	Castanas Elementary School	1,112	49
	Jose Rizal Elementary School	841	18
	Manuel L. Quezon Elementary School	858	42
	Morong Elementary School	227	27
	Pantoc Elementary School	166	22
	Pili Elementary School	272	22
	Sariaya East Central Elementary School	1,925	24
	Talaan Elementary School	440	15
	Tumbaga 1 Elementary School	481	42
	Tumbaga 2 Elementary School	328	46
TOTAL	8835	369	
Secondary	Canda National High School	1,049	103
	Sariaya National High School	682	98
	Castanas National High School	1,187	88
	Pili National High School	1,048	86
	TOTAL	3966	351

Research Instrument

A self-made questionnaire based mainly on the sub-problems of the study was designed and used by the researcher to collect data needed in the study. It was composed of two (2) parts. The first part of the questionnaire identified the parental engagement of the public elementary and secondary schools regarding Home Engagement, School Engagement, Child's Invitation, Teacher's Invitation, and General School Invitation. The second part determined the School Performance of the Public Elementary and Secondary Schools about Enrolment, Promotion, Retention, Drop-out, and Graduation Rate. The following scales were used:

Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	With Most Engagement
3.40 – 4.19	With More Engagement
2.60 – 3.39	With Moderate Engagement
1.80 – 2.59	With Less Engagement
1.00 – 1.79	With Least Engagement

Data Gathering Procedures

For the selection of a topic for the final investigation, the researcher submitted and proposed three research titles subject to the panel members' approval. After the title defense, the researcher immediately constructed and finalized the manuscript intended for proposal defense. After which, the first three chapters were written. It was presented to an esteemed group of oral examiners. After the scrutiny of the paper, with the fervent hope that the panelists would accept it, the proposal was given some minor revisions. It was advised that the remaining parts and chapters of the research be continued. Moreover, the researcher wrote and sent proper correspondence to the District Supervisor of the Sariaya East District and the principal of each school. The researcher personally visited the school and talked to the school heads of the aforementioned schools. The next step was to administer the questionnaire after the appropriate permits for the study's conduct had been approved. The researcher requested a meeting day with the school head to discuss the questionnaire with parents, specifically targeting the public secondary schools. The school head scheduled the brief meeting, and the distribution and retrieval were completed.

The researcher also asked each school about its performance of the school, such as enrollment rate, promotion rate, retention rate, drop-out rate, and graduation rate, for the last three years. On the other hand, actual limitations that serve as the pitfall of this research were discussed and included in the scope and delimitation. The data were statistically processed with the aid of Microsoft Excel. Thereafter, interpretation and analysis were done with the support of pertinent literature and studies. In addition, constant "check-ins" by the adviser were religiously observed as the study progressed.

Statistical Treatment of Data

After retrieval, the data were organized, tabulated, and analyzed using Microsoft Excel. Data were interpreted using descriptive statistics such as frequency and mean.

To determine the parental engagement, the mean is

$$M = \frac{\sum fx}{n}$$

Where:

$M = w$ mean

f = frequency

n = total number of respondents

The Kruskal-Wallis H-test was utilized to determine the significant difference between the responses. The Kruskal-Wallis H-test is a non-parametric statistical tool that compares two sample means from unrelated groups. This means that there are different people providing scores for each group. This test aims to determine if the samples are different from each other.

Formula

$$H = \frac{12}{NN + 1} \sum \frac{R_i^2}{n_i} - 3N + 1$$

n = the number in the i -th group

R_i = the total sum of ranks in the i -th group

To determine if there is a significant relationship between the two groups. Spearman rank-order correlation was used. Spearman rank-order correlation is a non-parametric tool to determine significant relationships between two variables.

Formula

$$r = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$$

Where,

- r =Spearman rank order Coefficient
- n = number of p
- d^2 =squared of the difference in ranks

RESULTS

Part I. Parental Engagement in Public Elementary and Secondary Schools in Sariaya East District, Division of Quezon.

Table 1. Level of Parental Engagement in Elementary School in Sariaya District in terms of Home Engagement

Statement	Frequency					Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. When my child's arrives home from school, I talk to him/her and ask to do his/her assignment.	254	99	8	4	4	4.61	With most engagement
2. I help my child in preparing his/her things especially when there are program at school.	257	94	12	2	4	4.62	With most engagement
3. I ask my child to finish doing his assignment and project before using cellular phone or any gaming gadgets.	251	105	0	11	2	4.60	With most engagement
4. I often explain challenging lesson or concept when he/she doesn't understand.	235	103	14	12	4	4.50	With most engagement
5. I teach my child to effectively manage his/her time between school works and household chores.	236	117	9	7	0	4.58	With most engagement
Overall Mean						4.58	With most engagement

Table 1 shows vital information about the *Level of Parental Engagement in Elementary School in Sariaya District in terms of Home Engagement*.

It was revealed in Table 1 that all gathered data from the responses of the respondents had generated an average of 4.58, which is verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." Statement 2, "I help my child in preparing his/her things especially when there are program at school," obtained the highest mean score of "4.62", ranked 1, and verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." On the other hand, Statement 4, "I often explain challenging lesson or concept when he/she doesn't understand," obtained the lowest mean score of 4.50, verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

The results from Table 1 affirm the critical role of parental engagement, particularly in the context of homework and school-related activities. This underscores the importance of fostering strong home-school partnerships to support students' holistic development within the Sariaya District's educational landscape. The findings suggest that while parents of the Elementary and Secondary schools in the Sariaya District demonstrate a commendable level of engagement in supporting their children's education at home, there is still room for improvement, particularly in ensuring that children receive adequate support in understanding challenging academic content. Addressing this gap could potentially further enhance the educational outcomes of students in the district.

Table 2. Level of Parental Engagement in Elementary School in Sariaya District in terms of School Engagement

Statement	Frequency					Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. I am motivated to attend meetings and visit the school because of the school's showcase of best practices such as conference with parents.	245	105	9	8	2	4.58	With most engagement
2. I gain valuable information on my child's development from school and it motivated me to attend school programs.	253	103	9	2	2	4.63	With most engagement
3. I find the plan provided by the school clear, practical and aligned to my child's success at school.	265	89	7	4	4	4.64	With most engagement
4. I commend the school for contacting me when my child has academic or behavioral issues, which is why I promptly go to schools.	265	95	5	4	0	4.68	With most engagement
5. I appreciate the school policies that encourage me to communicate regularly with teachers and the school.	269	87	9	8	8	4.68	With most engagement
Overall Mean						4.58	With most engagement

Table 2 presents vital information about the *Level of Parental Engagement in Elementary School in Sariaya District in terms of School Engagement*.

It was revealed in Table 2 that all gathered data from the responses had generated a weighted mean of 4.64, which is verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." Statement 4, "I commend the school for contacting me when my child has academic or behavioral issues, which is why I promptly go to schools." and Statement 5, "I appreciate the school policies that encourage me to communicate regularly with teachers and the school" obtained the highest mean score of "4.68", ranked one and verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." On the other hand, Statement 6, "I am motivated to attend meetings and visit the school because of the school's showcase of best practices such as conference with parents," obtained the lowest mean score of 4.58, verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

The results from Table 2 underscore the crucial role of parental engagement within the school environment, emphasizing the significance of collaboration between parents and educational institutions. The positive impact of parental involvement on student outcomes is evident, highlighting the need for continued efforts to foster strong partnerships between schools and families within the educational landscape of the Sariaya District. The findings also suggest that parents in the Sariaya District are actively engaged with the school and value communication and involvement in their child's education. Efforts to maintain effective communication channels and showcase school best practices can further strengthen parental engagement and contribute to positive outcomes for students in the district.

Table 3. Level of Parental Engagement in Elementary Level of School in Sariaya East District in terms of Response to Child's Invitation

Statement	Frequency					Mean	Qualitative Index
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. I attend the school activities especially if my child ask me to join events like family day and the like.	235	106	19	9	0	4.54	With most engagement
2. I visit the school when my child ask me to attend Parent-Teacher conference.	221	131	11	2	4	4.53	With most engagement
3. I attend the school meeting through my child invitation especially if it involves planning and improving school programs.	236	108	21	2	2	4.56	With most engagement
4. I visit the school if my child ask me to deal with conflict he/she involves.	230	123	14	0	2	4.57	With most engagement
5. I visit the school when there is card showing/distribution.	239	106	20	4	0	4.57	With most engagement
Overall Mean						4.55	With most engagement

Table 3 displays essential information about the *Level of Parental Engagement in Elementary School in Sariaya District in terms of response to Child Invitation*.

It was revealed in Table 3 that all gathered data from the responses had generated an average of 4.55, which is verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." Statement 4, "I visit the school if my child ask me to deal with conflict he/she involves," and Statement 5, "I visit the school when there is card showing/distribution," obtained the highest mean score of "4.57", ranked first and verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." On the other hand, Statement 2, "I visit the school when my child ask me to attend Parent-Teacher conference obtained the lowest mean score of 4.58 verbally interpreted as "with most engagement".

The results from Table 3 emphasize the importance of parental responsiveness to their child's invitations regarding school-related events and activities. This responsiveness fosters a sense of collaboration between parents, children, and schools, ultimately contributing to the overall success and well-being of students within the educational landscape of the Sariaya District. The findings also suggest that parents in the Sariaya East District are actively engaged and responsive to their child's invitations related to school activities. Efforts to further encourage parental participation in events such as Parent-Teacher conferences can contribute to stronger parent-school partnerships and ultimately benefit the educational experience of students in the district.

Table 4. Level of Parental Engagement in Elementary School in Sariaya District in terms of Response to Teacher's Invitation

Statement	Frequency					Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. I attend the teacher's invitation to a meeting because they provide clear information about the curriculum, programs and activities, as well as students' academic performance.	257	93	5	2	2	4.68	With most engagement
2. I immediately respond to teachers' invitation because they contact us, family or parents of students having academic or behavior problems.	209	151	6	1	2	4.53	With most engagement
3. I value the opportunity to participate in teacher invitation for a meeting as it's foster a supportive partnership between the teacher and parents.	199	155	11	2	2	4.48	With more engagement
4. I actively engage in discussion about my child's educational journey and ways to enhance to enhance their learning experience.	252	9	7	5	0	4.66	With most engagement
5. I prioritize attending the teachers' invitation for a conference or meeting as it's provide crucial insights to my child's educational journey.	241	115	10	3	0	4.61	With most engagement
Overall Mean						4.59	With most engagement

Table 4 shows vital information about the *Level of Parental Engagement in Elementary School in Sariaya District in terms of response to Teacher Invitation*.

It was revealed in Table 4 that all gathered data from the responses of the respondents had generated an average weighted mean of 4.59, which is verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." Statement 1, "I attend the teacher's invitation to a meeting because they provide clear information about the curriculum, programs and activities, as well as students' academic performance," obtained the highest mean score of "4.68", ranked one and verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." On the other hand, Statement 3, "I value the opportunity to participate in teacher invitation for a meeting as it's foster a supportive partnership between the teacher and parents," obtained the lowest mean score of 4.48, verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

The results from Table 4 underscore the critical role of effective teacher-parent communication and collaboration in fostering a supportive educational environment. When parents actively engage in teacher-involved activities and meetings, it contributes to a strengthened partnership between the school and home, ultimately benefiting students' academic success and well-being within the Sariaya District. This level of parental engagement, as reflected in the responses, signifies a positive commitment from parents to be actively involved in their child's educational journey, supporting the overall goals of the academic institutions within the district.

Table 5. Level of Parental Engagement in Elementary School in Sariaya District in terms of Response to General School's Invitation

Statement	Frequency					Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. I consider attending at school-wide events a valuable opportunity to connect with a wider school community and support my child's educational journey.	264	95	6	2	2	4.67	With most engagement
2. I actively participate in events that promote holistic approach to my child's development.	257	100	10	2	0	4.66	With most engagement
3. I attend school invitation to join in a school wide activity as it allow me to engage with teachers, and other parents, fostering a collaborative environment for the benefit of the students.	266	93	7	1	2	4.68	With most engagement
4. I appreciate the inclusive nature of attending school invitation to join in their program as it provide a platform for families to come together in support of our children's learning.	267	89	9	0	4	4.67	With most engagement
5. I respond to the school invitation because it reflects my commitment of being an active member of the school community and contributing to its positive environment.	259	100	6	2	2	4.66	With most engagement
Overall Mean						4.67	With most engagement

Table 5 illustrates vital information about the *Level of Parental Engagement in Elementary School in Sariaya District in terms of response to General School Invitation*.

It was revealed in Table 1 that all gathered data from the responses of the respondents had generated a weighted mean of 4.67, which is verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." Statement 3, "I attend the teacher's invitation to a meeting because they provide clear information about the curriculum, programs and activities, as well as students' academic performance," obtained the highest mean score of "4.68", rank one and verbally interpreted as "with most engagement" on the other hand, Statement 2, "I actively participate in events that promote holistic approach to my child's development" and Statement 5, "I respond to the school invitation because it reflects my commitment of being an active member of the school community and contributing to its positive environment" obtained the lowest mean score of 4.66, verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

The results from Table 5 underscore the crucial role of parental responsiveness to general school invitations, highlighting the positive outcomes of increased parental involvement in school-related events. This level of engagement signifies a firm commitment from parents to contribute to the school's positive environment and support their child's overall development. These findings emphasize creating inclusive and welcoming school environments that encourage parental involvement. When parents are actively engaged through general school invitations, it fosters a sense of partnership between parents, students, and the school community, ultimately benefiting students' educational experience and outcomes within the Sariaya District.

Table 6. Level of Parental Engagement in Secondary School in Sariaya District in terms of Home Engagement

Statement	Frequency					Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. When my child's arrives home from school, I talk to him/her and ask to do his/her assignment.	227	90	21	9	4	4.50	With most engagement
2. I help my child in preparing his/her things especially when there are program at school.	227	96	17	9	2	4.53	With most engagement
3. I ask my child to finish doing his assignment and project before using cellular phone or any gaming gadgets.	211	101	22	16	1	4.43	With more engagement
4. I often explain challenging lesson or concept when he/she doesn't understand.	210	93	17	27	4	4.36	With more engagement
5. I teach my child to effectively manage his/her time between school works and household chores.	213	104	16	12	6	4.44	With more engagement
Overall Mean						4.45	With more engagement

Table 6 depicts essential information about the *Level of Parental Engagement in Secondary School in Sariaya District in terms of Home Engagement*.

It was displayed in Table 6 that all gathered data from the responses of the respondents had generated a weighted mean of 4.45, which is verbally interpreted as "with more engagement." Statement 2, "I help my child in preparing his/her things especially when there are program at school," obtained the highest mean score of "4.53", ranking first and verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." On the other hand, Statement 4, "I often explain challenging lesson or concept when he/she doesn't understand," obtained the lowest mean score of 4.36, verbally interpreted as "with more engagement."

The results from Table 6 underscore the critical role of parental involvement in supporting their child's education at home, especially during the secondary school years. This level of engagement signifies a firm commitment from parents to provide the necessary support for their child's learning and development. These findings emphasize the importance of fostering a supportive home environment that encourages open communication, active involvement in school-related activities, and collaborative learning experiences. When parents are actively engaged in their child's education at home, it contributes significantly to improved student motivation, understanding, and academic success within the educational landscape of the Sariaya District.

Table 7. Level of Parental Engagement in Secondary School in Sariaya District in terms of School Engagement

Statement	Frequency					Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. I am motivated to attend meetings and visit the school because of the school's showcase of best practices such as conference with parents.	227	97	15	11	1	4.53	With most engagement
2. I gain valuable information on my child's development from school and it motivated me to attend school programs.	232	93	16	9	1	4.56	With most engagement
3. I find the plan provided by the school clear, practical and aligned to my child's success at school.	240	83	19	6	9	4.57	With most engagement
4. I commend the school for contacting me when my child has academic or behavioral issues, which is why I promptly go to schools.	243	86	8	14	0	4.59	With most engagement
5. I appreciate the school policies that encourage me to communicate regularly with teachers and the school.	252	78	11	6	4	4.61	With most engagement

Overall Mean	4.57	With most engagement
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Table 7 exhibits vital information about the *Level of Parental Engagement in Secondary School in Sariaya District in Terms of School Engagement*.

It was revealed in Table 1 that all gathered data from the responses of the respondents had generated an average of 4.57, which is verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." Statement 10, "I appreciate the school policies that encourage me to communicate regularly with teachers and the school," obtained the highest mean score of "4.61", ranked 1, and was verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." On the other hand, Statement 6, "I am motivated to attend meetings and visit the school because of the school's showcase of best practices such as conference with parents," obtained the lowest mean score of 4.53, verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

The results from Table 7 underscore the critical role of effective communication channels in fostering parental engagement with the school. Parents who appreciate school policies that encourage regular communication with teachers and the school demonstrate a higher level of involvement. However, even in cases where parents may need more motivation to attend meetings due to other commitments, there is still notable engagement within the school community.

These findings also emphasize the importance of creating a welcoming, inclusive school environment that encourages parental involvement. When parents are actively engaged in school-related activities and communication, it contributes significantly to improved student outcomes, positive school culture, and stronger school-parent partnerships within the educational landscape of the Sariaya District.

Table 8. *Level of Parental Engagement in Secondary School in Sariaya East District in Response to Child's Invitation*

Statement	Frequency					Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. I attend the school activities especially if my child ask me to join events like family day and the like.	219	98	25	9	0	4.50	With most engagement
2. I visit the school when my child ask me to attend Parent-Teacher conference.	200	124	16	8	3	4.45	With more engagement
3. I attend the school meeting through my child invitation especially if it involves planning and improving school programs.	214	102	30	4	1	4.49	With more engagement
4. I visit the school if my child ask me to deal with conflict he/she involves.	212	114	15	9	1	4.50	With most engagement
5. I visit the school when there is card showing/distribution.	223	97	21	7	3	4.51	With most engagement
Overall Mean						4.49	With more engagement

Table 8 shows vital information about the *Level of Parental Engagement in Secondary School in Sariaya District in Response to Child's Invitation*.

It was revealed in Table 8 that all gathered data from the responses of the respondents had generated a weighted mean of 4.49, which is verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." Statement 5, "I visit the school when there is card showing/distribution," obtained the highest mean score of "4.51", first in rank and verbally

interpreted as "with most engagement." On the other hand, Statement 2, "I visit the school when my child ask me to attend Parent-Teacher conference obtained the lowest mean score of 4.45, verbally interpreted as "with more engagement."

The results from Table 8 highlight the significant role of a child's invitation in fostering parental engagement with school events and activities. Parents who respond positively to their child's invitations create a supportive and participative school environment. These findings emphasize the importance of actively encouraging students to involve their parents in school events and activities. Parents attending events such as card showings, distributions, and other school functions at their child's invitation strengthens the parent-child bond and enhances the overall school-community relationships.

In conclusion, parents' positive response to their child's invitations reflects a commitment to supporting their child's educational journey. Such engagements contribute to a collaborative and vibrant school community within the Secondary Schools of the Sariaya District.

Table 9. Level of Parental Engagement in Secondary School in Sariaya East District in Terms of Response to Teacher's Invitation

Statement	Frequency					Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. I attend the teacher's invitation to a meeting because they provide clear information about the curriculum, programs and activities, as well as students' academic performance.	244	91	9	6	1	4.63	With most engagement
2. I immediately respond to teachers' invitation because they contact us, family or parents of students having academic or behavior problems.	191	145	7	7	1	4.48	With more engagement
3. I value the opportunity to participate in teacher invitation for a meeting as it's foster a supportive partnership between the teacher and parents.	181	148	17	4	1	4.44	With more engagement
4. I actively engage in discussion about my child's educational journey and ways to enhance to enhance their learning experience.	246	87	7	11	0	4.62	With most engagement
5. I prioritize attending the teachers' invitation for a conference or meeting as it's provide crucial insights to my child's educational journey.	224	109	8	7	3	4.55	With most engagement
Overall Mean						4.54	With most engagement

Table 9 displays essential information about the *Level of Parental Engagement in Secondary School in Sariaya District in Response to Teacher's Invitation*.

It was revealed in Table 9 that all gathered data from the responses of the respondents had generated an average weighted mean of 4.54, which is verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." Statement 1, "I attend the teacher's invitation to a meeting because they provide clear information about the curriculum, programs and activities, as well as students' academic performance," obtained the highest mean score of "4.63", ranked one and verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." On the other hand, Statement 3, "I value the opportunity to participate in teacher invitation for a meeting as it's foster a supportive partnership between the teacher and parents," obtained the lowest mean score of 4.44 and was verbally interpreted as "with more engagement."

The results from Table 9 highlight the crucial role of a teacher's invitation in facilitating parent-teacher communication and collaboration. Parents who actively attend meetings and events initiated by teachers demonstrate a strong commitment to their child's education and academic progress. These findings underscore the importance of clear communication and partnership-building between teachers and parents. Teachers providing clear information and inviting parents to participate in school activities foster a supportive and collaborative environment that benefits student learning and overall school culture.

Table 10. Level of Parental Engagement in Secondary School in Sariaya District in terms of Response to General School Invitation

Statement	Frequency					Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. I consider attending at school-wide events a valuable opportunity to connect with a wider school community and support my child's educational journey.	238	90	13	8	2	4.58	With most engagement
2. I actively participate in events that promote holistic approach to my child's development.	230	96	12	12	1	4.54	With most engagement
3. I attend school invitation to join in a school wide activity as it allow me to engage with teachers, and other parents, fostering a collaborative environment for the benefit of the students.	236	90	16	7	2	4.57	With most engagement
4. I appreciate the inclusive nature of attending school invitation to join in their program as it provide a platform for families to come together in support of our children's learning.	241	84	12	11	3	4.56	With most engagement
5. I respond to the school invitation because it reflects my commitment of being an active member of the school community and contributing to its positive environment.	239	91	5	8	8	4.55	With most engagement
Overall Mean						4.56	With most engagement

Table 10 shows vital information about the *Level of Parental Engagement in Secondary School in Sariaya District in Response to General School Invitation*.

It was revealed in Table 10 that all gathered data from the responses of the respondents had generated an average weighted mean of 4.56, which is verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." Statement 1, "I consider attending at school-wide events a valuable opportunity to connect with a wider school community and support my child's educational journey," obtained the highest mean score of "4.57", ranked one and verbally interpreted as "with most engagement." On the other hand, Statement 2, "I actively participate in events that promote holistic approach to my child's development," obtained the lowest mean score of 4.54 and was verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

The results from Table 10 underscore the vital role of school-wide invitations in fostering parental engagement and support for their child's educational journey. Parents who actively participate in school events contribute to a vibrant school community and play a crucial role in their child's overall development. These findings emphasize the importance of schools providing opportunities for parents to connect with the wider school community. When parents attend school-wide events and actively engage in activities

that promote holistic development, it creates a more enriching educational experience for students.

In conclusion, parents' positive response to school invitations reflects their commitment to being active participants in their child's schooling. The collaborative efforts between schools and parents, as highlighted in the results of Table 10, contribute significantly to a supportive and thriving educational environment within the Secondary Schools of the Sariaya District. This partnership between schools and parents is instrumental in fostering student success and overall well-being.

Part II. Performance Indicators of the Elementary and Secondary Schools in Sariaya East District

Table 11. Performance Indicators in Elementary Level

Elementary	Performance Indicators
Enrollment Rate	91.55
Promotion Rate	96.581
Retention Rate	97.293
Dropout Rate	0.775
Graduation Rate	97.846

Table 11 shows the performance indicators of schools at the elementary level in terms of Enrollment Rate, Promotion Rate, Retention Rate, Drop-out Rate, and Graduation Rate. It was revealed that in terms of enrollment rate, the elementary level achieved an average of 91.55, the promotion rate obtained 96.581, which can be seen as high, the retention rate established an average of 97.29 and can be interpreted that it was high retention, drop-out rate attained 0.775 which can be viewed as meager drop-out rate. The graduation rate was 97.846, which can be interpreted as a high rate. The high enrolment, promotion, retention, and graduation rates indicate that the elementary schools in the district are generally effective in ensuring student progression through grade levels and eventual completion of elementary education. This suggests a supportive and conducive learning environment that facilitates student success. In the same manner, the low drop-out rate indicates that the schools are successful in keeping students engaged and motivated to continue their education. This could be attributed to various factors such as effective teaching strategies, supportive school environments, and community involvement. The interpretation of these results suggests that while the elementary schools in the district are performing well in terms of student progression and retention, there may still be areas for improvement, particularly in addressing equity issues and further enhancing support systems for student success.

Table 12. Performance Indicators at Secondary Level

Secondary	Performance Indicator
Enrollment Rate	92.95
Promotion Rate	97.34
Retention Rate	97.875
Dropout Rate	1.168
Graduation Rate	97.008

Table 12 shows the performance indicators of schools at the Secondary Level in terms of Enrollment, Promotion, Retention, Drop-out, and Graduation rates. It was revealed that in terms of enrollment rate, the secondary level achieved an average of **92.95**, the promotion rate obtained **97.34**, which can be interpreted as a high promotion rate, and the retention rate established an average of **97.875** and was seen as high retention rate, drop-out rate attained **1.168** which can be viewed as low drop-out rate. The graduation rate achieved was **97.008**, which can be interpreted as high. The average enrollment rate indicates the number of students enrolled in secondary schools on average. This provides insight into the overall student population within the secondary education system. With regards to Promotion Rate which is considered high, it suggests that a significant majority of students are successfully progressing to the next grade level. This indicates a positive academic achievement and successful completion of grade-level requirements at the secondary level. Meanwhile, the retention rate signifies a high rate of students staying within the same grade level from one academic year to the next. This indicates that the secondary schools are effective in retaining students within their grade levels, potentially due to effective support systems or interventions aimed at addressing student needs and challenges. The drop-out rate is relatively low, indicating a minimal percentage of students leaving school before completing their secondary education. This suggests that the secondary schools are successful in keeping students engaged and supported, thus reducing the likelihood of drop-outs. And the graduation rate indicates a high percentage of students successfully completing their secondary education. This is a positive outcome as it reflects the effectiveness of the educational system in preparing students for higher education or entry into the workforce.

Part III. Significant Relationship between Parental Engagement and School Performance at Elementary and Secondary Level

Table 13. Significant Relationship between Parental Engagement and School Performance between the Elementary and Secondary Level

Level	Parental engagement	School Performance	r-value	p-value	Interpretation
Elementary	Parental engagement	Enrollment rate	0.47798	0.0837	Not Significant
	Parental engagement	Promotion rate	0.31498	0.27629	Not Significant
	Parental engagement	Retention rate	0.2489	0.39084	Not significant
	Parental engagement	Dropout rate	0.08159	0.71857	Not significant
	Parental engagement	Graduation rate	0.17769	0.54497	Not significant
Secondary level	Parental engagement	Enrollment rate	0	1	Not significant
	Parental engagement	Promotion rate	0.80	0.20	Not significant
	Parental engagement	Retention rate	0.40	0.60	Not significant
	Parental engagement	Dropout rate	0.20	0.8	Not significant
	Parental engagement	Graduation rate	0.20	0.80	Not significant

Table 13 depicts the correlation between Parental Engagement and School Performance at the elementary and secondary level.

At the elementary level, parental engagement and enrollment rate obtained an r-value of 0.47798 and a p-value of 0.0837 since $p\text{-value}=0.0837>0.05$; there is no significant relationship between parental engagement and enrollment rate at the elementary level. In terms of parental engagement and promotion rate obtained an r-value of 0.31498 and p-value of 0.27629 since $p\text{-value}=0.27629>0.05$, there is no significant relationship between parental engagement and promotion rate at the elementary level. Between parental engagement and retention rate obtained a r-value of 0.2489 and p-value of 0.39084 since $p\text{-value}=0.39084>0.05$, there is no significant relationship between parental engagement and retention rate at the elementary level. In terms of parental engagement and drop-out rate obtained a r-value of 0.08159 and p-value of 0.71857 since $p\text{-value}=0.71857>0.05$, there is no significant relationship between parental engagement and drop-out rate at the elementary level. Parental engagement and graduation rate obtained an r-value of 0.17769 and a p-value of 0.54497 since $p\text{-value}=0.54497>0.05$; there is no significant relationship between parental engagement

and graduation rate at the elementary level. The analysis explores the relationship between parental engagement and elementary-level school performance such as enrollment rate, promotion rate, retention rate, dropout rate, and graduation rate. Despite moderate to weak positive correlations observed between parental engagement and these outcomes, none of the correlations were statistically significant, as indicated by the p-values exceeding the standard significance level of 0.05. These findings suggest that while there may be trends suggesting associations between parental engagement and educational outcomes, these relationships lack statistical significance. Therefore, the data do not provide compelling evidence to support a significant impact of parental engagement on elementary-level school performance. Other factors beyond parental engagement likely play a more influential role in determining these outcomes, highlighting the complexity of factors influencing elementary education.

On the other hand, in the secondary level, parental engagement and enrollment rates obtained an r-value of 0 and a p-value of 1. Since $p\text{-value}=1>0.05$, there is no significant relationship between parental engagement and enrollment rate. In terms of parental engagement and promotion rate, an r-value of 0.80 and a p-value of 0.20 were obtained since $p\text{-value}=0.20>0.05$, and there is no significant relationship between parental engagement and promotion rate. The relationship between parental engagement and retention rate was received with an r-value of 0.40 and p-value of 0.60; since $p\text{-value}=0.60>0.05$, there is no significant relationship between parental engagement and retention rate. In terms of parental engagement and drop-out rate, an r-value of 0.20 and p-value of 0.80 were obtained, and since $p\text{-value}=0.80>0.05$, there is no significant relationship between parental engagement and drop-out rate. The analysis shifts to the secondary level, examining the association between parental engagement and various educational outcomes. The findings reveal no statistically significant relationships between parental engagement and enrollment rate, promotion rate, retention rate, or dropout rate. Despite varying correlation coefficients suggesting weak to moderate associations, all p-values exceed the conventional significance threshold of 0.05. Therefore, these results indicate that parental engagement does not significantly impact these secondary-level educational outcomes. This underscores the need to consider additional factors beyond parental involvement when understanding and addressing educational outcomes at the secondary level.

PART IV. Significant Difference on Parental Engagement between Elementary and Secondary Level

Parental Engagement	Level of Schools	X ²	p-value	Interpretation
Home Engagement	Elementary	4.5011	p=0.0339	There is significant difference
	Secondary			
School Engagement	Elementary	0.8995	p=0.3429	There is significant difference
	Secondary			
Response to Child's Invitation	Elementary	0.6497	p=0.4202	There is significant difference
	Secondary			
Response to Teacher's Invitation	Elementary	0.6497	p=0.4202	There is significant difference
	Secondary			
Response to General School Invitation	Elementary	3.2837	p=0.0699	There is significant difference
	Secondary			

Table 14. Significant Difference on Parental Engagement between Elementary and Secondary Level

Table 14 highlights the significant difference between on Parental Engagement between Elementary and Secondary level. The findings showed that there is no significant difference between parental engagement at the elementary and secondary levels regarding home engagement. The above hypotheses were tested using the Kruskal-Wallis Test. Using the P-value approach: The p-value is $p=0.0339$, and since $p=0.0339 < 0.05$, it is concluded that the null hypothesis is rejected. It is concluded that the null hypothesis *Ho is rejected*. Therefore, there is enough evidence to claim a significant difference between parental engagement at elementary and secondary levels in terms of home involvement at $\alpha=0.05$ significance level. Additionally, there is no significant difference between parental engagement at the elementary and secondary level in terms of school engagement. Using the p-value approach: The p-value is $p=0.3429$, and since $p=0.3429 > 0.05$, it has failed to reject the null hypothesis. It is concluded that the null hypothesis *Ho is accepted*. Therefore, there is enough evidence to claim that there is no significant difference between parental engagement in elementary and secondary levels in terms of school engagement at $\alpha=0.05$ significance level. Also, there is no significant difference between parental engagement at the elementary and secondary level in terms of response to child invitations. The above hypotheses were tested using the Kruskal-Wallis test. Using the P-value approach: The p-value is $p=0.3979$, and since $p=0.3979 > 0.05$, it has failed to reject the null hypothesis. It is concluded that the null hypothesis *Ho is accepted*. Therefore, there is enough evidence to claim that there is no significant difference between parental engagement at elementary and secondary levels in terms of response to child invitation at $\alpha=0.05$ significance level. Moreover, there is no significant difference between parental engagement at elementary and secondary levels in terms of response to teacher invitations. Using the p-value approach: The p-value is $p=0.4202$, and since $p=0.4202 > 0.05$, it has failed to reject the null hypothesis. It is concluded that the null hypothesis *Ho is accepted*. Therefore, there is enough evidence to claim that there is no significant difference between parental engagement at the elementary and secondary levels in response to teacher invitation at the $\alpha=0.05$ significance level.

And finally, there is no significant difference between parental engagement at the elementary and secondary level in terms of response to school invitations. Using the p-value approach: The p-value is $p=0.0699$, and since $p=0.0699>0.05$, it failed to reject the null hypothesis. It is concluded that the null hypothesis H_0 is *accepted*. Therefore, there is enough evidence to claim a significant difference between parental engagement at the elementary and secondary level in terms of response to school invitation at $\alpha=0.05$ significance level. The above analysis examines the differences in parental engagement between the elementary and secondary levels across various dimensions: home engagement, school engagement, response to child invitations, response to teacher invitations, and response to general school invitations. The findings indicate a significant difference in parental engagement between the two levels regarding home engagement, as evidenced by a p-value of 0.0339, indicating rejection of the null hypothesis. This suggests that parental engagement at the elementary and secondary levels differs significantly in terms of home engagement. However, no significant differences were found in parental engagement between the two levels concerning school engagement, response to child invitations, response to teacher invitations, and response to school invitations, as indicated by p-values exceeding 0.05. These results imply that while parental engagement varies between elementary and secondary levels in terms of home engagement, it remains relatively consistent across other dimensions. Understanding these differences can inform targeted interventions and support strategies to enhance parental engagement at both educational levels.

PART V. Significant Difference on Performance Indicators between Elementary and Secondary Level

Table 15. Significant Difference between Performance Indicators of Public Elementary and Secondary Level

Performance Indicators	Rank total (elementary)	Rank total (secondary)	h-value	Critical value @0.05	Interpretation
Enrollment rate	118	53	2.5376	3.8415	No significant difference
Promotion rate	119.5	51.5	2.055	3.8415	No significant difference
Retention rate	126	45	0.5526	3.8415	No significant difference
Dropout rate	110	43	-10.459	3.8415	No significant difference
Graduation rate	144	27	1.3647	3.8415	No significant difference

Table 15 contains the rank total, h-value, critical value, and interpretation of elementary and secondary levels of school performance.

In terms of **enrollment rate**, the elementary has a rank total of "**118**" while the secondary has a rank total of "**53**". They obtain an H-value of "**2.5376**" and a critical value of "**3.8415**" at 0.05 level of significance since the H-value < critical value. There is no

sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, the enrollment rate at the elementary and secondary levels is the same. Regarding **promotion rate**, the elementary has a rank total of "**119.5**" while the secondary has a rank total of "**51.5**". They obtain an H-value of "**2.055**" and a critical value of "**3.8415**" at 0.05 level of significance since the H-value < critical value. There is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, elementary and secondary levels are similar in terms of promotion rates. Regarding **retention rate**, the elementary has a rank total of "**126**" while the secondary has a rank total of "**45**". They obtain an H-value of "**0.5526**" and a critical value of "**3.8415**" at 0.05 level of significance since the H-value < critical value. There is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is no significant difference between elementary and secondary levels in terms of retention rate. In terms of **drop-out rate**, the elementary has a rank total of "**110**" while the secondary has a rank total of "**43**". They obtain a H-value of "**-10.459**" and a critical value of "**3.841**" at 0.05 level of significance since H-value < critical value. There is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the elementary level and secondary level in terms of drop-out rate. In terms of **graduation rate**, the elementary has a rank total of "**144**" while the secondary has a rank total of "**27**". They obtain a H-value of "**1.3647**" and a critical value of "**3.8415**" at 0.05 level of significance since H-value < critical value. There is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the elementary and secondary levels in terms of graduation rate.

The above analysis compares enrollment rate, promotion rate, retention rate, dropout rate, and graduation rate between the elementary and secondary levels. The results reveal no significant differences between these educational levels across all the examined metrics. In terms of enrollment rate, promotion rate, retention rate, dropout rate, and graduation rate, the obtained H-values are below the critical value at the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests that enrollment, promotion, retention, dropout, and graduation rates remain similar between elementary and secondary levels. These findings imply that factors influencing these educational outcomes may be consistent across both educational stages or that any differences are not significant enough to be detected in this analysis. Further research could explore additional factors or conduct a more in-depth examination to better understand any nuanced differences between the elementary and secondary levels regarding these educational outcomes. Understanding such nuances can inform targeted interventions and policies aimed at improving educational outcomes across both levels.

PART VI. The proposed Sustainability Program is presented in Appendix A. This proposed program/plan will help to continuously develop strategic actions to sustain high performance in enrollment, promotion, retention, graduation rate, and drop-out rate with the support of both internal and external stakeholders.

The sustainability program for parental engagement is designed to uphold and enhance the enrolment, promotion, graduation, and retention rates of students attending public elementary and secondary schools within Sariaya East District. By fostering collaboration between parents, educators, and the community, the program aims to

create a supportive environment conducive to academic success and holistic student development.

DISCUSSION

Summary of Findings

1. Level of Parental Engagement in Sariaya East District, Division of Quezon.

1.1 Elementary

1.1.1 In terms of Home Engagement, all data gathered from the respondents' responses generated an average mean of 4.58, verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

1.1.2 In terms of School Engagement, all data gathered from the respondents' responses had generated an average mean of 4.64, which was verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

1.1.3 In terms of response to Child's Invitation, all data gathered from the respondents' responses generated an average mean of 4.55, which was verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

1.1.4 In terms of Response to Teacher's Invitation, all data gathered from the respondents' responses generated an average mean of 4.59, verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

1.1.5 In terms of Response to General School's Invitation, all data gathered from the respondents' responses had generated an average mean of 4.67, which was verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

1.2 Secondary

1.2.1 In terms of Home Engagement, all data gathered from the respondents' responses generated an average mean of 4.45, verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

1.2.2 In terms of School Engagement, all data gathered from the respondents' responses generated an average mean of 4.57, which was verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

1.2.3 In terms of response to Child's Invitation, all data gathered from the respondents' responses generated an average mean of 4.49 verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

1.2.4 In terms of Response to Teacher's Invitation, all data gathered from the respondents' responses generated an average mean of 4.54, which was verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

1.2.5 In terms of Response to General School's Invitation, all data gathered from the respondents' responses generated an average mean of 4.56, which was verbally interpreted as "with most engagement."

2. Performance Indicators in Sariaya East District, Division of Quezon.

2.1 Elementary

2.1.1 It was revealed that the elementary level obtained a rate of 659.619 in terms of enrollment rate.

2.1.2 It was revealed that the elementary level obtained a rate of 96.581 in terms of promotion rate.

2.1.3 It was revealed that the elementary level obtained a rate of 97.293 in terms of retention rate.

2.1.4 It was revealed that the elementary level obtained a rate of 0.775 in terms of drop-out rate.

2.1.5 It was revealed that the elementary level obtained a rate of 97.846 in terms of graduation rate.

2.2 Secondary

2.2.1 It was revealed that the secondary level obtained a rate of 917.167 in terms of enrollment rate.

2.2.2 It was revealed that the secondary level obtained a rate of 97.34 in promotion rate.

2.2.3 It was revealed that the secondary level obtained a rate of 97.875 in terms of retention rate.

2.2.4 It was revealed that the secondary level obtained a rate of 1.168 in terms of drop-out rate.

2.2.5 It was revealed that the secondary level obtained a rate of 97.008 in terms of graduation rate.

3. It was found that there is no significant statistical relationship between parental engagement and performance indicators at both the elementary and secondary levels. The analysis revealed no significant statistical relationship between parental

engagement and enrollment, promotion, retention, drop-out, or graduation rates at the elementary and secondary levels.

4. The results revealed no statistical difference in parental engagement between elementary and secondary schools in Sariaya East District, Division of Quezon.
 - 4.1 In the elementary level, parental engagement and enrollment rate obtained an r-value of 0.47798 and a p-value of 0.0837 while in secondary r-value of 0 and a p-value of 1.
 - 4.2 In terms of parental engagement and promotion rate, the rate obtained an r-value of 0.91498, a p-value of 0.27629, a secondary r-value of 0.80, and a p-value of 0.20.
 - 4.3 Between parental engagement and retention, the rate obtained an r-value of 0.2849 and p-value of 0.39084 and a secondary r-value of 0.40 and p-value of 0.60.
 - 4.4 In terms of parental engagement and drop-out rate, it obtained an r-value of 0.08159, and p-value of 0.71857, and a secondary r-value of 0.20 and p-value of 0.80.
 - 4.5 Parental engagement and graduation rate obtained an r-value of 0.0.17769, a p-value of 0.54497, a secondary r-value of 0.20, and a p-value of 0.80.
5. The results revealed no significant difference in the performance indicator between elementary and secondary schools in Sariaya, East District.
 - 5.1 In terms of enrollment rate, the elementary has a rank total of "118" while the secondary has a rank total of "53". They obtain an H-value of "2.5376" and a critical value of "3.8415" at 0.05 level of significance since the H-value < critical value.
 - 5.2 In terms of promotion rate, the elementary has a rank total of "119.5" while the secondary has a rank total of "51.5". They obtain an H-value of "2.055" and a critical value of "3.8415" at 0.05 level of significance since the H-value < critical value.
 - 5.3 In terms of retention rate, the elementary has a rank total of "126" while the secondary has a rank total of "45". They obtain an H-value of "0.5526" and a critical value of "3.8415" at 0.05 level of significance since the H-value < critical value.
 - 5.4 In terms of drop-out rate, the elementary has a rank total of "110" while the secondary has a rank total of "43". They obtain an H-value of "-10.459" and a critical value of "3.841" at 0.05 level of significance since H-value < critical value.

5.5 Lastly, considering the graduation rate, the elementary has a rank total of "144" while the secondary has a rank total of "27". They obtain an H-value of "1.3647" and a critical value of "3.8415" at 0.05 level of significance since H-value < critical value.

6. Based on the results of the study, the researcher proposed a sustainability program. This proposed program shall help continuously develop strategic actions to sustain high performance in enrollment, promotion, retention, graduation rate, and drop-out rate with the support of internal and external stakeholders

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are presented:

1. Parental engagement, as interpreted through the lens of "With Most Engagement," underscores a notable level of active participation and commitment by parents within Elementary and Secondary Education settings. This finding suggests a pervasive and significant involvement of parents in various activities pertaining to these educational domains. Such high levels of engagement imply a robust partnership between schools and parents, which is essential for fostering positive academic outcomes and overall student success. Moving forward, continued efforts to encourage and support parental involvement can further enhance the educational experience and outcomes for students at these levels.
2. The performance indicators evaluated across elementary and secondary education levels have demonstrated commendable results, evidenced by high enrolment, promotion, retention, and graduation rates. Particularly noteworthy is the significantly low dropout rate, which indicates a resilient educational ecosystem where students are effectively supported and motivated to persist in their academic journey. These findings underscore the effectiveness of educational policies, programs, and interventions aimed at bolstering student engagement, academic progress, and ultimately, successful transitions through various educational milestones. Moving forward, continued emphasis on strategies to further mitigate dropout risks while sustaining positive performance indicators will be paramount in ensuring equitable access to quality education and fostering lifelong learning outcomes.
3. Analysis of parental engagement across diverse educational outcomes at both elementary and secondary levels yields no statistically significant relationships with enrollment, promotion, retention, dropout, or graduation rates. This suggests that while parental involvement is undoubtedly important for fostering a supportive educational environment, its direct impact on these specific outcome measures may be limited within the context of this study. Further research exploring nuanced aspects of parental engagement and its potential correlations with educational outcomes could provide deeper insights into the complex dynamics at play. Nonetheless, the absence of significant relationships underscores the multifaceted nature of factors influencing student success, urging educators and policymakers to consider a holistic approach in promoting positive educational outcomes.

4. The results revealed no significant difference in parental engagement between elementary and secondary schools in Sariaya, East District, where most parents were engaged in all school activities.
 5. The results revealed no significant difference in the performance indicator between elementary and secondary schools in Sariaya, East District, wherein enrolment, promotion, retention, and graduation have high progression rates and drop-out rates were significantly low.
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Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Sustaining parental engagement in school activities is essential, alongside the encouragement of school-initiated programs that facilitate increased participation of parents/guardians. This collaborative approach fosters a synergistic relationship in delivering educational services and contributes to the attainment of elevated learning outcomes.
2. It is advisable for the school to consistently formulate strategic measures aimed at upholding high performance in areas such as enrolment, promotion, retention, graduation rates, and the reduction of drop-out rates, with the active involvement and support of both internal and external stakeholders. This collaborative effort ensures the ongoing enhancement of educational outcomes and the sustained success of the institution.
3. While acknowledging the significance of parental engagement, it's important to recognize that it may not singularly dictate educational metrics. Therefore, there is a need for further research to delve into additional variables that potentially impact student progress. Emphasizing the multifaceted nature of academic success, such investigations can provide a more comprehensive understanding, informing strategies that effectively support students in achieving their educational goals.
4. Collaboration between the school and parents is crucial in cultivating a supportive and conducive environment for student advancement and success throughout their educational journey. Emphasizing the significance of effective educational strategies and support mechanisms within this partnership is essential. By working together, both parties can enhance student learning experiences and facilitate their overall academic achievement.
5. Encouraging collaboration between schools and parents is paramount in achieving educational outcomes for students at both elementary and secondary levels. This collaborative effort should aim to enhance various educational indicators, reflecting a conducive environment for high student progression, retention, and success. Such outcomes underscore the effectiveness of existing educational strategies and support systems, emphasizing the importance of continued partnership between schools and parents in promoting student achievement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study ensured the informed consent was given to the following respondents. Freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interests exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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